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RESEARCH ARTICLE

HiFINS: A Hierarchical Federated Learning-Based Interactive System for Smart Home Security

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ABSTRACT As smart home environments grow increasingly populated with heterogeneous and resource-constrained IoT devices, ensuring secure and adaptive network protection has become a critical challenge. Traditional intrusion detection solutions, i.e., centralized, rule-based, or cloud-dependent, struggle to scale or provide user-friendly insights for non-technical residents. To address these limitations, we propose *HiFINS*, a *Hierarchical Federated Learning-based Interactive Network Security* system that integrates hierarchical federated learning (*HiF*) for real-time, privacy-aware threat detection and a human-centered interface (*INS*) for intuitive security management. HiFINS distributes model training across home routers, local servers, and edge/cloud infrastructure, enhancing detection performance while minimizing data exposure. Simultaneously, the interactive application enables users to configure routers, view alerts, and respond to threats without needing technical expertise. The system is implemented and validated within a reproducible, container-based test environment that emulates realistic smart home conditions and facilitates transparent benchmarking. Experimental results show that HiFINS outperforms both centralized and existing hierarchical federated approaches in terms of detection accuracy, inference throughput, and precision, while maintaining competitive training efficiency. These gains demonstrate HiFINS's practical viability for securing home networks in real time. Although the hierarchical design introduces coordination overhead, the tradeoff enables more resilient and scalable deployment across diverse environments. The system's modular and reproducible structure supports future adaptation and integration into broader smart home security efforts.

INDEX TERMS Federate learning, IoT, smart home system, intrusion detection system, HCI.

I. INTRODUCTION

As smart home environments become increasingly saturated with interconnected devices, ensuring network security has emerged as a critical challenge. Devices ranging from IP cameras and smart plugs to voice assistants continuously generate network traffic, making them vulnerable to a wide spectrum of cyber threats such as unauthorized access, malware propagation, and distributed denial-of-service attacks [1].

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Unlike traditional enterprise networks, smart homes exhibit highly dynamic, heterogeneous behavior, with intermittent connectivity, limited device resources, and minimal administrative oversight. These characteristics make conventional security enforcement particularly difficult. Traditional security solutions, e.g., cloud-centric or rule-based intrusion detection systems, are consistently inadequate in these settings due to limitations in scalability [2], adaptability [3], and user accessibility [4]. Their reliance on centralized data aggregation introduces latency and privacy risks, while their rigid rule sets are often ineffective against novel or evolving

FIGURE 1. Overview of the HiFINS framework highlighting the integration of hierarchical federated learning, cloud–edge collaboration, intelligent human–computer interaction, and reproducibility for end-to-end smart home network security.

attack vectors [5]. Moreover, many of these systems are designed with technically skilled users in mind, offering complex configurations and log outputs that overwhelm or confuse the average resident [6]. As a result, there is a pressing need for a new generation of security systems that can operate efficiently in resource-constrained environments, adapt to diverse usage patterns, and present actionable insights through interfaces that empower non-technical users.

Figure 1 illustrates the core components required to secure modern smart home networks through a dynamic, privacy-preserving, and user-centered architecture. At the foundation is Hierarchical Federated Learning, which enables secure and distributed model training across edge and cloud tiers. Cloud and Edge Collaboration ensures scalable infrastructure with consistent communication and adaptive threat modeling. Reproducibility allows for replicable evaluation and deployment through structured experimentation platforms. Intelligent Human–Computer Interaction (HCI) serves as the front end, translating technical insights into clear, actionable feedback for users. Collectively, these components converge to support a robust HiFINS (Hierarchical Federated Interactive Network Security) framework for protecting residential IoT systems.

To address these challenges, we propose a novel two-part solution composed of: (1) HiF, a hierarchical federated learning framework that enables privacy-aware, scalable, and real-time threat detection by distributing learning responsibilities across edge devices, edge servers, and a cloud-based global model coordinator; and (2) INS, an interactive network security interface built for non-technical smart home users. This interface integrates detection feedback, router configuration, threat notifications, and assistant-guided decision support into a single desktop application designed for usability and transparency.

The full HiFINS system is implemented and evaluated in a reproducible edge–cloud testbed environment using the

Chameleon Cloud platform [7]. Our experiments combine live smart home traffic collected through real devices and a standardized public dataset, CICIoT2023 [8], to evaluate accuracy, responsiveness, and scalability under real-world conditions. We compare HiFINS against two representative models: a centralized training system (Flower [9]) and a recent hierarchical federated framework (Flight [10]), assessing their detection capabilities, training efficiency, and system overhead. Our evaluation demonstrates that HiFINS significantly improves intrusion detection accuracy and efficiency compared to existing centralized and federated learning baselines. It reduces false positives and accelerates inference throughput, making it well-suited for real-time smart home environments. While achieving higher detection reliability and faster processing, HiFINS also strikes a balance between model performance and training time. However, these gains come with tradeoffs in system complexity and resource coordination, particularly during hierarchical scheduling and federated synchronization.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work; Section III introduces the system architecture and design; Section IV presents the HiF hierarchical federated learning methodology; Section V outlines the INS human-centered interactive networking security system; Section VI provides the evaluation; and Section VII concludes with a summary and discussion of future work.

II. RELATED WORKS

With the rise of IoT-enabled smart homes, researchers have increasingly explored federated learning (FL) to support intrusion detection without compromising data privacy. Researchers believe FL is a beneficial solution for securing vulnerable IoT environments due to its nature as a privacy-aware machine learning model [31]. While traditional machine learning algorithms suffer issues such as privacy leakage and high computational overhead, FL models address privacy issues by maintaining privacy of data while sharing information with different devices [32]. A growing body of work has extended FL into hierarchical architectures to improve convergence, accuracy, and scalability in distributed environments [11]. Some efforts have introduced multi-tiered FL models to support collaborative learning across edge and cloud levels [11], [13], [33], while others have augmented these frameworks with trust-aware mechanisms [15], [34] or energy-efficient components like spiking neural networks [14]. However, these designs often rely on abstract architectural assumptions and lack practical integration into smart home infrastructure. Our work builds on these hierarchical designs by anchoring the learning process at the router level, enabling fast, localized detection while embedding a trust mechanism into the learning pipeline for resilience against poisoning and misbehaving nodes.

Complementary to learning architectures, several studies have examined the role of edge computing in enhancing

TABLE 1. Comparison of related smart home security system with HiFINS (our proposed solution).

System	Hierarchical	Uses FL	Edge/ Constrained Support	Privacy Focus	Real-time IDS Focus	HCI
<i>Related Research Systems</i>						
Saadat et al. [11] and zhang et al. [12]	✓	✓	✓	Implicit	N/A	×
Sarhan, Mohanad and Lo [13]	✓	✓	✓	✓ Strong	N/A	×
Aouedi & Piamrat (SURFS) [14]	✓	✓	✓	Implicit	N/A	×
Amiri-Zarandi et al. (SIDS) [15]	× (None)	✓	Limited	✓ Strong	×	×
Bourechak et al. [16]	× (None)	N/A	✓	N/A	✓	×
Sewak et al. [17]	× (None)	× (RL)	×	N/A	✓	×
Yang et al. [18] and Gupta, Lav [19]	✓ (Cloud-Edge)	× (ML)	✓	× (None)	✓	×
Mishra et al. [20]	✓ (Edge)	× (BC/ML)	✓	Limited	×	×
Chhetri & Motti [21]	× (None)	×	Limited	✓ Strong	×	✓ Strong
Prange et al. [22]	× (None)	×	Limited	Implicit	×	✓ Strong
Saiyed et al. [23]	× (None)	×	✓	N/A	✓	✓ Strong
Mothukuri et al. [24]	× (None)	✓	✓	✓ Strong	N/A	×
Cui et al. [25]	✓ (Proposed)	✓	✓	✓ Strong	Limited	×
Jabez et al. [26]	× (None)	×	✓	N/A	✓	×
Alhartomi et al. [27]	× (None)	× (ML)	✓	×	×	Limited
Vansiya et al. [28]	✓ (Cloud-Edge)	× (ML/DL)	✓	Limited	✓	×
Bach et al. [29]	×	× (ML)	×	Limited	×	✓ Strong
Khan et al. [30]	×	×	✓	×	×	Limited
HiFINS (ours)	✓	✓	✓ (Strong)	✓ Strong	✓ (Strong)	✓ Strong

system responsiveness and reducing latency [16]. The integration of AI capabilities at the network edge has been shown to enable timely analytics and decentralized decision-making [18]. Deep reinforcement learning has also been explored as a way to introduce adaptability into IDS systems, particularly in changing attack environments [17], [35], [36]. Yet, many of these frameworks are either centralized or assume full trust in the data plane, limiting their applicability in privacy-sensitive home settings [37]. We address this gap by combining edge-level deployment with federated adversarial training, allowing our system to learn from localized traffic patterns without ever transferring raw data off-site.

Efforts to enhance trust and integrity in IDS systems have also looked toward blockchain and decentralized consensus mechanisms. Blockchain has been proposed as a secure backbone for federated aggregation, offering auditability and resilience to tampering [20], [25], [38]. Other approaches have developed asynchronous and decentralized FL protocols to mitigate communication bottlenecks and prevent single points of failure [25], [39]. FL methods using GRU-based anomaly detection while maintaining data privacy through encrypted model updates have also been proposed [24]. While these innovations advance system robustness, they often come with increased complexity and limited support for lightweight deployment in consumer-grade environments. In contrast, our system adopts blockchain-inspired verification methods within a lightweight FL stack designed for household routers, maintaining efficiency while upholding data integrity.

User interaction and explainability have emerged as critical components in smart home security. Interactive configuration tools and persuasive design strategies have been proposed to guide users toward secure settings [21], [22], [28], and explainable ML models have been developed to help users interpret IDS alerts and system behavior [23], [29]. Although these efforts highlight the importance of human-centered design, they are typically isolated from the underlying learning architecture and lack integration with real-time intrusion detection. Our approach bridges this gap by embedding explainable modules directly into the IDS interface, enabling homeowners to understand, configure, and respond to threats within the same platform that performs decentralized detection.

Finally, the trend toward domain-specialized IDS systems reflects the recognition that generic security models fail to capture the nuances of specific environments. Tailored FL models have been fine-tuned for contexts like transportation networks and smart homes [40], [41], emphasizing the need for contextual sensitivity in both data modeling and system response. Parallel work has explored early anomaly detection mechanisms using statistical or outlier-based methods [26]. These approaches support the idea that threat identification should begin as early as possible in the network lifecycle. Our work unifies these advances by delivering a smart home-specific IDS that performs early-stage detection directly at the network ingress point, guided by federated training routines that reflect the unique traffic profiles and device diversity found in modern households. In addition, recent research has advanced low-power hardware

acceleration of recurrent models, emphasizing digit-serial DA-based fixed-point RNN architectures and compact VLSI designs for LSTM networks [30]. These developments enable efficient on-device inference for IoT end-nodes, supporting early anomaly filtering and reduced communication overhead in federated settings [27].

In summary, while previous studies have laid important groundwork across hierarchical learning, edge intelligence, privacy preservation, human factors, and domain adaptation, our contribution lies in synthesizing these dimensions into a unified, router-level federated IDS system. A detailed comparison of related approaches is provided in Table 1, which highlights the distinct architectural, privacy-preserving, and user-facing strengths of our proposed solution relative to existing methods.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND DESIGN

In this section, we detail our multi-layered smart home security framework by providing a step-by-step workflow for the whole logic. In addition to that, we provide a detailed system architecture, offering a breakdown of each component within the front-end and back-end design.

A. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION DISCUSSION

The proliferation of interconnected devices within smart home environments has introduced a wide range of security vulnerabilities, exacerbated by the heterogeneity and dynamic behavior of IoT networks. Traditional security solutions, typically centralized and reactive, often fail to adapt to the nuanced and context-dependent nature of threats in such environments. These limitations are especially pronounced in scenarios involving vulnerable populations—such as elderly residents—where security breaches may intersect with issues of safety, autonomy, and privacy. To address these challenges, we propose *HiFINS*: a *Hierarchical Federated Learning-based Interactive Network Security* system designed for real-time, privacy-preserving anomaly detection and user-in-the-loop threat response.

HiFINS is grounded in both real-world network observations and the CICIoT2023 [8] dataset, a state-of-the-art resource for evaluating intrusion detection models in smart IoT infrastructures. The CICIoT2023 dataset offers a comprehensive and meticulously curated representation of benign and malicious traffic across various IoT protocols and devices, simulating diverse and realistic usage scenarios. It includes high-fidelity emulations of common smart home behaviors as well as sophisticated cyber-attacks, enabling robust training and validation of learning-based IDS models. In parallel, we have collected localized network data from actual smart home routers and sensors, reflecting routine user interactions and context-specific device usage patterns. This hybrid dataset foundation ensures that HiFINS is both empirically grounded and generalizable across heterogeneous deployments.

Importantly, HiFINS is not limited to passive detection. By incorporating an intuitive, user-facing interface, the

system facilitates real-time feedback from residents. For instance, if anomalous activity such as an unscheduled door opening or unusual vital sign reading is detected, the resident is prompted to verify or flag the event. This interactive design enhances detection precision over time while respecting the user's privacy and autonomy. In critical cases, and only with user consent, the system can escalate alerts to caregivers or emergency services. Through this human-centered, federated approach, HiFINS advances a new paradigm of smart home security—one that is adaptive, privacy-preserving, and responsive to the complex needs of connected living spaces.

In the following sub-section, we present the design and implementation of HiFINS in general, emphasizing its architectural components, federated learning mechanisms, and interactive security features. In addition to that, we also highlight how HiFINS distinguishes itself in its comprehensive, real-time, and user-integrated approach to smart home intrusion detection.

B. HiFINS ARCHITECTURE AND COMPONENT OVERVIEW

The HiFINS system architecture, as illustrated in Figure 2, operates in a cyclic, hierarchical manner that spans smart home routers, local edge devices, and cloud-based federated learning infrastructure. It begins with **Smart Home Data Collection**, where a variety of IoT devices (e.g., smart speakers, cameras, and plugs) generate continuous network traffic. This traffic is intercepted by a smart router enhanced with monitoring capabilities such as `tcpdump`, `Wireshark`, and `Nmap`, enabling comprehensive packet-level inspection. These routers serve as the initial data collection point and enforce first-line security monitoring by passively observing all incoming and outgoing device communications.

Once the raw traffic data is captured, it is processed within the **Local-HiF** (See Section III-A) module. Here, packet flows are gathered and filtered, with irrelevant features removed and benign traffic (e.g., from whitelisted IPs) excluded to reduce noise. Leveraging tools such as `Scapy` and `TensorFlow`, the cleaned data is used to fine-tune an anomaly detection model trained to recognize malicious or abnormal activity patterns specific to the local home network. This model is updated incrementally as new training data accumulates, enabling real-time detection of evolving threats.

Upon local model refinement, the learned parameters (instead of the real-data) are securely transmitted using `gRPC` and integrated with the federated learning framework implemented via `Flower` [9]. These updates are sent to the **Global-HiF** component, where multiple local models from other homes are aggregated using `FedAvg` [42]. This stage combines incoming model weights, augments training data with pre-labeled samples, and produces an optimized global model. Pre-training is also conducted using a curated dataset at a centralized HPC server to ensure all participants benefit from a strong initialization, regardless of their local data sparsity.

FIGURE 2. Overview flowchart of HiFINS (Hierarchical federated learning-based interactive system) for smart home networking data collection, analysis and interpretation utilizing local and global federated learning models.

Closing the loop, the newly synthesized global model is distributed back to each participating Local-HiF module for continued fine-tuning, creating a feedback mechanism that enhances detection accuracy over time while maintaining full data locality and privacy. Throughout this process, HiFINS ensures that no raw traffic logs or identifiable user data ever leave the smart home environment.

Tightly integrated with this workflow is the **Interactive Network Security System (INS)**, which bridges system intelligence and user control via an interactive network management user interface (UI). Built using React, Electron, and Flask, this desktop-based dashboard visualizes network behavior, security alerts, and system status in real time. It empowers users to review detected anomalies, adjust security preferences, and optionally trigger responsive actions such as device quarantine or notification of trusted third parties (e.g., caregivers or emergency responders).

Together, these four components, i.e., Smart Home Data Collection, Local-HiF, Global-HiF, and INS, form a comprehensive, privacy-preserving, and user-interactive intrusion detection ecosystem. HiFINS distributes intelligence across a hierarchical network architecture, leverages federated learning for scalable collaboration, and fosters human-in-the-loop feedback for adaptive smart home protection. By unifying edge learning, real-time responsiveness, and intuitive interaction, HiFINS offers a novel, resilient solution to the increasingly complex cybersecurity landscape of modern smart environments. While the HiFINS architecture is fundamentally hierarchical, consisting of the Router (Data Collector), Local-HiF (Edge Server), and Global-HiF (Cloud HPC), it is designed with inherent modularity to maximize adoption. The complete three-tier coordination is implemented as our proposed solution to achieve superior performance, privacy, and global threat intelligence. However, for simpler smart home setups with limited resources (e.g., only a router and no dedicated edge server), the Local-HiF component's core detection capabilities can be directly integrated into the router, enabling a functional two-tier deployment (Router + Cloud) or even a single-tier deployment (Router-Local-HiF integrated) for completely localized, privacy-preserving threat detection. This inherent

flexibility ensures that the complexity is an optional feature that scales with the user's need for efficiency and intelligence.

IV. HiF: HIERARCHICAL FEDERATED LEARNING METHODOLOGY

In this section, we first introduce the overall workflow of HiF (Hierarchical Federated Learning), outlining its layered architecture across edge devices, edge servers, and the cloud. We then detail the training algorithms used in both the Local-HiF and Global-HiF models, and summarize with the benefits of the Hierarchical Federated Learning algorithm design.

A. ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

To address the increasing complexity of smart home cybersecurity, we introduce a redesigned Hierarchical Federated Learning (HFL) architecture, as shown in Figure 3. This framework decentralizes the training process across three distinct layers: edge devices, edge servers, and a centralized HPC cloud server. The hierarchical design enhances scalability, reduces detection latency, and maintains user data privacy. Traditional federated learning systems rely on a single coordination point, which limits flexibility and adaptability. In contrast, HFL introduces a multi-tiered structure that allows collaboration among distributed clients and regional aggregators.

The first layer involves edge devices, such as smart speakers, cameras, and plugs. These devices perform real-time intrusion detection by monitoring local network traffic. Each device runs a Local-HiF module, which includes both anomaly detection and adversarial detection components. The models deployed at this layer are trained using both real-world data collected from smart homes and benchmarked samples from the CICIoT2023 dataset. The edge devices do not share raw traffic data. Instead, they extract feature representations and transmit model updates to the next layer for aggregation. This preserves privacy while maintaining local responsiveness.

The second layer consists of edge servers, such as Jetson boards, Raspberry Pi clusters, and nodes on the Chameleon testbed. These servers receive model updates from multiple

FIGURE 3. Hierarchical federated learning model update workflow for smart home IoT network intrusion detection.

edge devices and act as local aggregation points. The Local-HiF module at this level includes advanced training strategies. These strategies involve cross-validation, data augmentation, synthetic training using generative models, and real-data contextualization. A discriminator model is used to filter noisy or low-quality model contributions. This refinement ensures that only validated and representative model updates are forwarded for global aggregation. TensorFlow serves as the backend for model training and evaluation at this stage.

The final layer in the hierarchy is the HPC cloud server, which coordinates the Global-HiF module. This server aggregates model updates from all edge servers across the system. It synthesizes a global model that reflects a broad understanding of threats across different environments. Before deployment, the global model is further enhanced using pretrained data and baseline knowledge. The cloud component is hosted on Chameleon infrastructure, which provides scalable computational resources suitable for deep learning workloads. The updated global model is then redistributed to edge servers, which in turn deliver the model to their connected edge devices.

The communication and aggregation processes across all three layers are managed using the Flower framework. In our implementation, the Flower framework has been extensively redesigned to support hierarchical federation. It now enables separate aggregation routines at the edge

and cloud levels, supporting flexible learning topologies and adaptive communication schedules. This architectural change makes the system resilient to client availability, network disruptions, and non-iid data distributions.

Each component of the HFL pipeline contributes to a continuous feedback loop. The system allows edge devices to benefit from collective intelligence without ever exposing sensitive data. Detection models are refined at each level before being pushed back to devices, completing the cycle. As a result, the HiFINS architecture achieves high detection accuracy, efficient model updates, and strong privacy guarantees. It is suitable for a wide range of smart home and IoT security deployments.

The Auxiliary Conditional Tabular Discriminator Sub-model (Discriminator) assists the Local-HiF in detecting adversarial data to prevent data poisoning attacks. The Discriminator is capable of detecting network anomalies as well due to being trained in differentiating between real benign data, real attack data, and fake data. Although the Discriminator is pre-trained during the AC-GAN training process, The Discriminator is also taught alongside the Local-HiF. This is a fine-tuning process for the Discriminator in comprehending real data to better discern adversarial threats. To clarify this mechanism, the Discriminator’s training occurs continuously in parallel with the fine-tuning of Local-HiF. Specifically, it uses an asynchronous, less computationally expensive process to quickly absorb new

network traffic data as training samples, assuming the data contains no adversarial threats for faster learning.

During training, the discriminator and Local-HiF operate in a cooperative learning loop. The discriminator is initially pre-trained using a combination of benign, malicious, and synthetically generated samples to learn decision boundaries between trustworthy and adversarial inputs. In each local training round, the discriminator first evaluates newly collected network data, assigning confidence scores that determine whether samples are passed to or withheld from the Local-HiF model. The Local-HiF then performs anomaly classification on the filtered set, and its loss gradients are back-propagated jointly with the discriminator's adversarial-detection loss. This dual-objective optimization allows the discriminator to improve its filtering precision while helping the Local-HiF focus on reliable, high-quality samples. Through this coordinated fine-tuning process, HiFINS achieves greater robustness against data-poisoning and low-fidelity model updates, ensuring that each federated round reflects cleaner and more representative local traffic behavior.

The Discriminator has the unique advantage of being able to intake new network traffic data faster due to certain training sessions where the system can assume that there are no adversarial threats and can intake the network data as training data for the Discriminator to learn upon while there is a much longer and sophisticated process to extract training data for the Local-HiF sub-model. The Discriminator can also intake the same data as the Local-HiF sub-model to fine-tune in detecting network anomalies. The two sub-models work alongside each other. In certain conditions, the processes vary, where the Discriminator filters the data before the Local-HiF intakes it to detect attacks, or the Discriminator and Local-HiF cross-validate each other's prediction on intrusive data. The Discriminator here acts as a trust mechanism, validating that the incoming model update performs as expected against archived real and adversarial data, ensuring resilience against poisoning attacks before the update is accepted and archived for future training. This faster intake capability allows it to rapidly establish a baseline of 'normal' traffic diversity, which is crucial for its subsequent role in model contribution filtering. Figure 3 demonstrates when the fine-tuned global models go to the edge server, after advanced training, the global models get cross-validated by both the server's Local-HiF Model and Discriminator Model.

B. LOCAL FEDERATED TRAINING ALGORITHM

The Local Federated Training Algorithm (Algorithm 1), i.e., *Local-HiF*, is designed to support both localized and federated model training in edge-based hierarchical federated learning environments. Its primary purpose is to enable edge devices or edge servers to perform anomaly detection training based on their own data without transferring raw traffic externally, thereby preserving privacy while allowing collective learning. The *Local-HiF* algorithm implements two distinct operational modes to accommodate varying

Algorithm 1 Local Federated Training (*Local-HiF*)

```

1: Input: Dataset selection, model type, training mode,
   hyperparameters, optional pretrained models
2: Output: Trained model and evaluation results
3: Parse Arguments:
   Dataset, model type, training mode, epochs, pre-
   trained models, etc.
4: Configure:
   Determine dataset and preprocessing settings
   Select training area (Localized or Federated)
   Configure model training type (ClientOnly, HostFitO-
   nEnd)
5: Initialize:
   Load and preprocess dataset using datasetLoadPro-
   cess
   Load model hyperparameters using hyperparameter-
   Loading
   Create or load models using modelCreateLoad
6: Initiate Training:
7: if TrainingArea == Federated then
8:   Load federated training configuration via modelFed-
   eratedTrainingConfigLoad
9:   Set server_address based on selected host
10:  Join federated training session via Flower framework
11:   Edge Server Client Federated Procedure:
12:   Send local model parameters using
   client.get_parameters()
13:   Set global parameters and perform local training
   with client.fit()
14:   Evaluate local model using client.evaluate()
15: else
16:   Load localized training configuration via modelCen-
   tralTrainingConfigLoad
17:   Train model using client.fit()
18:   Evaluate model using client.evaluate()
19:   Save trained model locally via client.save()
20: end if

```

resource availability: (i) Localized Mode, and (ii) Federated Mode. In the newly detailed Localized Mode, the Edge Server operates autonomously; it performs model training and updates exclusively using local data and refrains from weight aggregation with the *Global-HiF* server. This mode ensures real-time security without the need for external coordination. The more complex Federated Mode leverages the full hierarchical design, reserved for environments where multiple edge servers or high-performance requirements necessitate centralized coordination and global threat learning. This inherent flexibility ensuring that simple, resource-constrained users can benefit from immediate security without the overhead of full hierarchical deployment.

The algorithm begins by parsing the necessary arguments including the dataset source, model type, training mode, and any optional pretrained models. These parameters guide the

Algorithm 2 Edge Server Federated Learning Client Initialization and Training for *Local-HiF*

```

1: procedure InitializeESClient(model, dataset, node, config, data, dp_params, training, callbacks, logs)
2:   Store model, dataset info, and node ID
3:   Set flags: DP,
4:   Load train/test/val datasets
5:   Set training hyperparameters and DP settings
6:   Set callback parameters: metrics, modes
7:   if DP_enabled then
8:     Create and assign DP optimizer with clipping and noise
9:   Compile model with DP optimizer and metrics
10:  else
11:    Compile model with standard Adam optimizer and metrics
12:  end if
13:  Print model summary
14: end procedure
15: procedure get_parameters(config)
16:  return model weights
17: end procedure
18: procedure fit(parameters, config)
19:  Increment round counter
20:  Print current round number
21:  Record start time
22:  Set model weights to received parameters
23:  Train model with training and validation data using callbacks
24:  Record end time and calculate elapsed time
25:  Extract training and validation loss
26:  Record training metrics to log file
27:  return model weights, number of samples, and empty dict
28: end procedure

```

subsequent configuration phase, where preprocessing options are determined, training mode is selected (i.e., Localized or Federated), and the model training type is configured. If the training mode is set to federated, the algorithm loads the federated configuration (line 11), establishes the server address, and connects to the training host using the Flower framework. Once connected, it enters the federated training procedure (line 14), where the edge server client interacts with the federation lifecycle: sending local model weights (line 15), receiving global parameters and performing local training with `client.fit()` (line 16), and evaluating the model using `client.evaluate()` (line 17). Alternatively, in localized training mode, the model is trained and evaluated without network communication (lines 18–21). The model is fitted to the local dataset using `client.fit()`, evaluated via `client.evaluate()`, and then saved locally for potential future deployment.

The internal mechanisms of the edge server’s federated learning client are defined in Algorithm 2, which supports initialization, training, and communication during a federated round. The `InitializeESClient` procedure sets up the environment by storing model and node identifiers, loading datasets, configuring training parameters, and setting differential privacy (DP) settings if enabled (lines 1–11). If DP is active, an optimizer is created with gradient clipping and noise addition for privacy-preserving training; otherwise, a standard Adam optimizer is used (lines 6–10). During each federated round, the initialization function returns the current model weights to the aggregator (line 14). When the aggregator calls fit function, the client sets the received parameters, trains the model on its local dataset using validation data and callbacks, logs the results, and returns the updated weights (lines 17–25). These returned weights contribute to the next global aggregation step.

Together, these algorithms enable flexible, privacy-aware model training and evaluation in the hierarchical structure of HiFINS. The *Local-HiF* algorithm allows edge servers to act as intermediate learners and aggregators, preparing locally optimized models before pushing them to the Global-HiF coordinator. This design supports adaptive model personalization while ensuring system-wide convergence and robustness across diverse edge environments.

Algorithm 3 Global Federated Learning (*Global-HiF*)

```

1: Input: Dataset selection, model type, training mode, hyperparameters, optional pretrained models
2: Output: Trained model and evaluation results
3: Parse Arguments:
   Dataset, model type, training mode, epochs, pre-trained models, etc.
4: Configure:
   Determine dataset and preprocessing settings
   Select type of federated Training (Default, FitOnEnd, Save, or Load)
   Configure model training type (ClientOnly, HostFitOnEnd)
5: if no server load, save, or fitOnEnd flags then
6:   Run server with default FedAvg strategy
7: else
8:   Initialize:
   Load and preprocess dataset using datasetLoadProcess
   Load model hyperparameters using hyperparameterLoading
   Create or load models using modelCreateLoad
   ▷ Advanced Training After Global Model Update
9:   Run server with advanced strategy
   IDSSFitOnEndStrategy
10: end if

```

C. GLOBAL FEDERATED LEARNING ALGORITHM

The Global-HiF training process governs the final stage of the hierarchical federated learning pipeline, where aggregated

Algorithm 4 IDSFitOnEndStrategy Initialization and Training for *Global-HiF*

```

1: procedure InitializeIDSFitOnEndStrategy(model components, data, configs, callbacks)
2:   Store discriminator, generator, and NIDS model
3:   Assign dataset, node info, DP flag, and augmentation portion
4:   Set data splits for training, validation, and test
5:   Set training hyperparameters and DP parameters
6: end procedure
7: procedure initialize_parameters(client_manager)
8:   if serverLoad is True then
9:     Return pre-trained NIDS model weights
10:  else
11:    Return None
12:  end if
13: end procedure
14: procedure aggregate_fit(server_round, results, failures)
15:   Increment round count
16:   Aggregate client updates via FedAvg
17:   if aggregation successful then
18:     Set NIDS model weights to aggregated values
19:   end if
20:   if DP is enabled then
21:     Compile model with DPKerasAdamOptimizer
22:   else
23:     Compile with standard Adam optimizer
24:   end if
25:   Train NIDS model using updated training data and callbacks
26:   Save trained model to file
27:   Log training metrics and loss values
28:   return model weights and empty config dict
29: end procedure

```

model updates from distributed edge servers are refined and synthesized into a robust global model. As shown in Algorithm 3, the global controller begins by parsing key parameters, including the dataset selection, model type, and training strategy. It supports various federation modes such as default FedAvg, Save, Load, and the enhanced FitOnEnd refinement procedure (line 1-6). When a fit-on-end flag is detected, the server initializes advanced training resources, including data pipelines and model structures (lines 10–12). This setup phase prepares the model for post-aggregation fine-tuning using enriched, globally visible training data.

The IDSFitOnEndStrategy, detailed in Algorithm 4, encapsulates this refinement logic. Upon initialization, the server stores the model components (including any adversarial discriminators or generators), sets data splits for training, validation, and testing, and configures privacy settings and augmentation proportions (lines 1–5). When client updates are received, the server aggregates them using the standard FedAvg method (line 11). The global model is then

conditionally recompiled, either with a differential privacy (DP) optimizer or a standard Adam optimizer, depending on configuration (lines 14–16). A global retraining step follows, using updated data partitions and callbacks to improve generalization and robustness (line 17). This internal fine-tuning, performed entirely on the server-side, ensures enhanced detection performance while maintaining strict data locality guarantees. Only anonymized, updated model weights are returned after training (line 20), thus preserving privacy while closing the hierarchical learning loop.

By incorporating this fit-on-end refinement strategy, Global-HiF elevates standard federated learning workflows. It leverages the full context of aggregated knowledge without violating privacy constraints. This novel enhancement improves intrusion detection accuracy system-wide and ensures the global model remains adaptive and resilient in heterogeneous smart home environments.

To formally describe the optimization process, the HiFINS learning objective integrates multiple sources of information—including local traffic features, adversarial filtering signals, and user feedback—into a unified loss function. The overall objective is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{HiFINS}} = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}} + \gamma \mathcal{L}_{\text{fb}},$$

where \mathcal{L}_{CE} is the standard cross-entropy loss for anomaly classification based on preprocessed flow-level features extracted from packet captures, \mathcal{L}_{adv} represents the adversarial loss generated by the discriminator that penalizes misclassified or low-confidence samples, and \mathcal{L}_{fb} denotes the feedback-aware component derived from user-labeled data collected through the INS dashboard. During each local training round, router-level modules first normalize and encode statistical attributes of traffic—such as packet length variance, flow duration, and entropy—into tabular tensors for TensorFlow processing. User feedback labels (“benign,” “suspicious,” or “confirmed threat”) are appended asynchronously to this dataset and treated as weighted supervised samples governed by the coefficient γ . The combination of these three objectives allows HiFINS to continuously refine its intrusion detection boundaries, enhance resilience to adversarial contamination, and adapt to evolving user interactions while maintaining strict data locality through federated synchronization.

In the implemented HiFINS framework, the loss components introduced above are instantiated using standard cross-entropy objectives tailored for different sub-tasks within the hierarchical training process. Specifically, the discriminator branch employs Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) to evaluate the validity of adversarial or benign samples, while the Local-HiF classifier utilizes Categorical Cross-Entropy (CCE) to perform multi-class intrusion categorization. The user feedback module contributes to the feedback-aware term \mathcal{L}_{fb} , which adjusts model gradients based on user-confirmed or dismissed alerts collected through the INS dashboard. Feedback entries are first encoded using the `LabelEncoder` utility from the `scikit-learn`

(`sklearn`) library and transformed into NumPy tensor arrays to maintain compatibility with TensorFlow's input pipeline. These tensors are concatenated with feature vectors derived from packet-level statistics—including flow duration, packet length variance, and entropy—to construct a multimodal training dataset for local optimization. Model updates are performed through a combination of gradient descent and adversarial fine-tuning, depending on the current phase of the Hierarchical Federated Learning (HFL) cycle. During federated synchronization, only model weights are exchanged across participants using the FedAvg aggregation algorithm, ensuring that privacy is preserved while enabling continuous refinement of both the Local-HiF and Discriminator models. This training strategy unifies local adaptation, adversarial robustness, and user-driven feedback into a coherent optimization framework for privacy-preserving smart home intrusion detection.

In summarize, the core advantage of the *Local-HiF* design lies in its ability to balance localized training efficiency with strict data privacy. By enabling edge servers to independently process, train, and manage model updates based on observed network traffic, *Local-HiF* supports flexible deployment in diverse smart home environments. Feature extraction is the first step in this process, where key attributes such as packet length, flow duration, and protocol types are derived from PCAP data. To safeguard privacy, sensitive identifiers like IP addresses and ports are anonymized. These processed features form the basis for training localized models, which are periodically updated through federated synchronization without transmitting raw data. This decentralized approach ensures each edge device adapts to its environment while contributing to the global detection model.

During training, each edge node uses TensorFlow [43] to fine-tune its local intrusion detection model. Model weights are periodically sent to coordinating edge servers or central node via the Flower framework, which we have redesigned to support hierarchical federation. The edge server aggregates these weights, applies refinement procedures, and forwards the result to a *Global-HiF* server hosted on the Chameleon Cloud. The updated global model is then redistributed to all participating nodes for real-time inference. This hierarchical loop—training at the edge, aggregation at the server, and global optimization at the cloud—enables continuous learning while preserving privacy. By organizing federated learning across these layers, HiFINS delivers scalable and adaptive intrusion detection for smart home and IoT environments.

V. INS: HUMAN-CENTERED INTERACTIVE NETWORKING SECURITY SYSTEM DESIGN

In this section, we detailed our human-centered Interactive Networking Security System (INS) in two parts, i.e., front-end design with main user interface components description, and back-end design combined with the interface communication logic. After that, we discussed the reproducible

implementation of the whole system with the need of edge and cloud collaboration.

A. USER INTERFACE COMPONENTS AND FRONT-END SYSTEM DESIGN

To ensure accessibility, transparency, and usability for non-technical users, HiFINS integrates an Interactive Network Security System (INS) that bridges advanced intrusion detection with intuitive, human-centered design. Unlike traditional cybersecurity tools that often rely on complex configurations and technical terminology, INS simplifies the interaction by providing focused, easy-to-navigate visual components that support setup, monitoring, and response. As shown in Figure 4, the interface integrates six coordinated modules that guide users through system operation while ensuring real-time access to key security insights.

The interface begins with the *Sidebar Navigation* (top-left in Figure 4), which organizes core system functions into a vertical panel. This layout provides access to pages such as Home, Network Status, IoT Devices, Notifications, and Settings. Each option is clearly labeled and accompanied by a large icon, enabling quick recognition and minimizing the need to memorize technical terms. This design ensures that users can move between tasks such as checking device status or reviewing security alerts without needing prior experience with network tools.

The *Router Configuration Interface* (top-center) supports initial setup by allowing users to enter their router brand, model, and IP address through guided dropdown menus. Validation occurs in real time, and contextual prompts help users confirm correct inputs. Once configuration is complete, the system automatically communicates with the router through secure SSH using Paramiko. This enables packet capture and initiates device discovery, which identifies connected edge nodes for use in the HiFINS detection process. This automation removes the need for manual command-line configuration or network scanning by the user.

Assistance during setup and troubleshooting is provided by the *NetBot Assistant Panel* (top-right), which delivers real-time feedback and instructional guidance in a conversational format. Rather than requiring users to consult external help resources, NetBot interprets internal system data to offer relevant suggestions. For example, if a router misconfiguration is detected or a classifier update is available, NetBot prompts the user with suggestions or explanations. It responds to the current system state and helps resolve issues without needing technical support.

Security events detected by HiFINS are summarized in the *Notifications Console* (bottom-left), which converts technical anomaly logs into clear messages. Each entry includes a timestamp, a brief description of the event, and a severity indicator using a simple color system. Users can acknowledge messages to avoid duplicate alerts. Events are generated automatically by edge inference engines and streamed through Flask to this console. This helps users

FIGURE 4. Comprehensive network security dashboard for hifins interactive networking security system.

stay aware of network activity and prioritize potential threats without needing to interpret raw logs.

To provide an overview of network health, the *Security Status Card* (bottom-center) presents key information such as the current number of detected threats, device statuses, and network name. Changes in the detection model or alert state are reflected immediately. If a threat is found, the label changes from “Secure” to “Attention Needed.” If the model is updating, a temporary message appears. This summary helps users understand system behavior at a glance without digging through submenus.

The *Bandwidth Usage Chart* (bottom-right) shows traffic patterns over time in a simplified bar graph format. Usage is categorized by daily or hourly ranges to help users detect unexpected spikes or unusual patterns. When the system flags abnormal behavior, the chart highlights the corresponding bar and links directly to the Notifications Console for details. This visualization provides a straightforward way to connect network performance with security alerts.

The front-end design not only presents data but facilitates the human-in-the-loop validation essential for HiFINS’s long-term accuracy. For instance, the Notifications Console (bottom-left) presents clear, simplified alerts from complex anomaly logs. When users acknowledge, dismiss, or respond to an alert, that interaction provides implicit, high-fidelity feedback. This feedback is immediately fed back to the Flask server, which uses it to refine the Local-HiF discriminator’s thresholds, effectively minimizing the persistent false positives often found in heterogeneous network traffic. This continuous user validation cycle is the mechanism that ensures the model remains adapted to the household’s unique, evolving traffic patterns over the long term. Altogether, the

FIGURE 5. Comprehensive network security dashboard for smart home intrusion detection and monitoring.

INS component of HiFINS transforms complex security functions into a clear, accessible experience. It supports the federated learning system in the background while presenting relevant updates and decisions in an understandable format. By combining real-time data processing with a focused human-centered design, INS ensures that normal smart home users can engage with cybersecurity effectively and confidently.

B. INTERFACE COMMUNICATION LOGIC AND BACK-END SYSTEM DESIGN

Figure 5 presents the integrated architecture of the HiFINS platform, detailing how system components interact across local, edge, and cloud environments. This layered design enables secure, responsive, and scalable intrusion detection, while supporting real-time communication and model

coordination among all devices involved in the smart home ecosystem.

At the base of the data acquisition layer, a private router running OpenWRT and equipped with packet monitoring tools such as tcpdump, Wireshark, and Nmap is responsible for collecting raw network traffic. These tools continuously monitor communication between IoT devices and external networks. The collected packets are streamed to the local edge infrastructure through secure SSH-based communication protocols, which are managed using Paramiko, a Python library for remote command execution and file transfer.

The local communication and control logic is managed through a lightweight Python-based Flask server. This local server acts as the core interface between frontend components and backend services. It receives traffic data from the OpenWRT router, interacts with edge devices for task delegation, and maintains status synchronization with the user interface application. The application itself is built with React.js and Electron.js, providing a cross-platform graphical dashboard that allows users to manage router configurations, review alerts, and view live system health indicators. All data passed between the user interface and backend services is securely managed via the Flask API layer.

Connected to this local control layer are the edge devices, which include lightweight nodes such as Raspberry Pi and Jetson Nano. These devices run real-time classifiers trained using TensorFlow, performing intrusion detection directly on captured packet features. In standalone mode, each edge device can function independently, detecting threats and reporting alerts to the Flask server. When operating within a hierarchical federated learning configuration, these edge devices receive model updates from connected edge servers, enabling continuous improvement based on collective insights.

Edge servers, often deployed on Chameleon Cloud nodes, serve as regional aggregation points in the hierarchical learning topology. These servers coordinate training across multiple nearby edge devices by collecting model parameters, performing federated averaging, and pushing the optimized weights back to the clients. The servers also execute higher-level model fine-tuning tasks using TensorFlow, augmenting the dataset with synthetic traffic patterns or adversarial scenarios. All coordination between edge servers and the Flask-managed control plane is handled through encrypted communication protocols, maintaining secure multi-device orchestration within the local network.

At the highest level, cloud servers act as global federated coordinators and model repositories. Hosted on remote HPC nodes (e.g., within the Chameleon infrastructure), these servers are responsible for pre-training global models and managing top-tier federated aggregation. The cloud orchestrates interactions between edge servers through a modified federated learning backend using the Flower framework, enabling synchronized global model updates. Each cloud node maintains communication with its edge-tier counterparts, ensuring that insights generated locally can

propagate system-wide without requiring direct access to raw user data.

The back-end system addresses practical deployment challenges, particularly maintaining reliable data ingress from the constrained router environment. Secure SSH communication via Paramiko manages the deployment of monitoring tools like tcpdump and Wireshark on the OpenWRT router. This logic includes automated connection health checks and re-establishment routines to mitigate data loss due to intermittent connectivity or device reboots—a common long-term challenge in consumer-grade smart homes. Furthermore, the Flask server manages the secure storage of encrypted configuration files and ensures that all communication with the front-end remains lightweight, maintaining system responsiveness even on resource-constrained Jetson Nano and Raspberry Pi edge devices. By integrating these components, the HiFINS architecture enables a privacy-preserving, real-time, and adaptive security solution. Edge devices perform real-time inference, edge servers conduct collaborative training, and cloud nodes maintain federated consistency across the system. All layers are tightly coordinated via secure protocols and modular APIs, ensuring robust communication logic while preserving user autonomy and system reproducibility.

VI. EVALUATION

In this section, we present the experimental setup, describe and justify the datasets used, and introduce the baseline methods for comparison. We define key evaluation metrics for both detection performance and system efficiency. Finally, we analyze results from multiple angles to highlight HiFINS's advantages over traditional and advanced models.

A. EXPERIMENT SETUP

To validate the effectiveness of the HiFINS architecture in real-world smart home environments, we deployed a fully integrated system involving the router-level capture interface, local server coordination, federated edge servers, and the desktop application interface. This setup builds directly on the communication flow and hierarchical learning strategies outlined in earlier sections, ensuring synchronized, low-latency operation across all layers.

The user-facing desktop application, developed using React.js and Electron.js, serves as the primary interface for configuring the network and initiating the detection system. During the initial setup, users input router credentials including the IP address, SSH port, and admin login. These values are securely stored using encrypted configuration files. Once initialized, the desktop application launches a Python-based local Flask server, which connects to the OpenWRT router using Paramiko. This secure SSH connection enables real-time retrieval of router diagnostics such as CPU usage, network interface states, and firewall rule status.

Upon successful connection, the Flask server deploys monitoring tools including tcpdump and Wireshark on the OpenWRT router. These tools capture packet-level traffic,

TABLE 2. Hardware and software specifications of the HiFINS system and experiment setups.

Component	Specifications	Function
Router	OpenWRT-based GL-MT300N-V2; tcpdump, Wireshark, Nmap	Real-time network traffic capture and diagnostics collection
Local Server	Intel NUC, 8GB RAM, Ubuntu 20.04; Flask, Paramiko, Python	Packet preprocessing, SSH coordination, feature extraction, local-to-edge communication
Edge Servers (1 & 2)	AWS EC2 t3.medium (4 vCPUs, 8GB RAM); TensorFlow, Flower, Local-HiF	Federated training, model aggregation, threat model refinement
Desktop Application	Electron.js frontend, React.js UI, Flask backend	User interface for configuration, alert visualization, and model status feedback
Communication Framework	Secure SSH via Paramiko; local Flask API	Encrypted router interaction, federated model transfer, and backend synchronization
Data Pipeline	PCAP traces, feature vectors (JSON); custom parsing scripts	Traffic filtering, benign/malicious flow identification, feature generation for training
Edge Inference Nodes	Raspberry Pi 4 or Jetson Nano; TensorFlow Lite	On-device anomaly detection, real-time model inference deployment

producing PCAP files that are securely transferred to the local server for preprocessing. The preprocessing pipeline removes routine or benign traffic by filtering known addresses and traffic patterns. Extracted features are formatted into training data suitable for federated learning and passed to upstream edge servers for collaborative analysis.

The local server runs on an Intel NUC with 8GB RAM and handles all local data ingestion, feature extraction, and model synchronization. Two federated learning edge servers—hosted on AWS virtual machines with 4 vCPUs and 8GB RAM each—are responsible for training intrusion detection models based on the distributed data received from local servers. These nodes execute the Local-HiF algorithm, update the classifiers using TensorFlow, and push optimized models back to the local environment.

Model coordination is handled by a lightweight Flask process that manages the full exchange of model parameters and inference outcomes between the local node and the federated edge servers. Once a training round completes, the updated model is integrated into the local detection stack, and the desktop application is refreshed with security alerts and live network insights. This cycle supports real-time detection, decentralized learning, and privacy-aware threat intelligence.

To summarize the experimental deployment, Table 2 outlines the hardware specifications, software tools, and configuration roles of each system component involved in the HiFINS evaluation.

B. DATASET DESCRIPTION AND JUSTIFICATION

To support the development and evaluation of the HiFINS intrusion detection system, we utilize a combination of controlled traffic captures and publicly available benchmark datasets. This hybrid approach ensures that the system benefits from both realistic deployment data and standardized evaluation baselines, providing a comprehensive foundation for training and validation.

One key dataset employed during the training phase is the CICIOT2023 dataset [8], a curated collection of IoT network traffic that includes a diverse set of benign behaviors and well-defined malicious activities. This dataset simulates a variety of real-world attack scenarios, including distributed denial-of-service (DDoS), port scanning, and botnet infiltration. The traffic is captured across heterogeneous IoT devices and network configurations, making it suitable for evaluating generalization across device types, communication protocols, and threat vectors. Its structured labeling and multi-modal

traffic streams allow for accurate benchmarking of intrusion detection models, particularly when assessing detection accuracy, false positives, and model adaptability.

In addition to the dataset, we incorporate real-world traffic collected directly from our HiFINS deployment environment. During the system's development and pre-deployment phase, network packets were captured from a smart home router configured with OpenWRT, utilizing packet inspection tools such as tcpdump and Wireshark. This traffic includes normal device interactions, configuration errors, and emulated threat patterns, forming a representative training set that reflects realistic user behavior and device usage.

These real-world captures were used exclusively for initial system training and testing purposes. Once HiFINS is deployed, all collected traffic remains stored locally on the user's device. This design aligns with the system's privacy-preserving objective, ensuring that sensitive user data never leaves the smart home environment. During runtime, HiFINS extracts non-identifiable statistical features from live traffic streams and uses them solely for local inference or aggregated federated updates, without exposing raw packet content to external servers.

The combined use of CICIOT2023 and real-world traffic captures enables HiFINS to be trained on diverse and meaningful data while preserving user privacy post-deployment. This strategy ensures the system can identify both well-known and emerging threats in varied smart home conditions, supporting its adaptive and robust detection performance across real-world scenarios.

C. REPRODUCIBLE EDGE AND CLOUD COLLABORATION

To support rigorous experimentation and reproducibility, our HiFINS framework is deployed and evaluated in a structured edge–cloud testbed environment, as illustrated in Figure 6. This architecture comprises three hierarchical tiers: local edge devices, intermediate edge servers, and a remote high-performance computing (HPC) server hosted in a cloud network. Each tier is responsible for specific functions—local training at the device level, model aggregation and validation at the edge server level, and global coordination and advanced training at the cloud level. This layered design enables reproducible deployment of federated learning workflows under varying network and resource constraints.

We utilize the Chameleon Cloud testbed to facilitate consistent and scalable testing across heterogeneous devices and configurations. Chameleon's flexible infrastructure sup-

FIGURE 6. Hierarchical federated learning architecture for distributed intrusion detection.

ports edge computing scenarios by integrating real-world local networks (e.g., OpenWRT routers, Raspberry Pi, and Jetson Nano devices) with virtualized edge servers and GPU-enabled cloud instances. Using the Chi@TACC [44] site and its fabnetv4 network, we connect bare-metal resources across distributed tiers for seamless synchronization of training and model distribution. Chameleon’s automated experiment management and image-based provisioning allow researchers to define, launch, and replicate the entire HiFINS deployment stack—from software environments to data movement pipelines—with minimal overhead.

While HiFINS adopts a three-tier hierarchical design for scalability and federated coordination, the architecture remains modular and can be simplified for smaller deployments. In household or small-office environments where intermediate edge servers may not be available, the router can directly federate with the cloud coordinator through the same Flower-based communication layer. In this two-tier mode, the router handles local inference and lightweight model updates, while the cloud performs global aggregation and refinement. This configuration minimizes deployment overhead and preserves data privacy without requiring dedicated edge hardware. Conversely, in large-scale research or enterprise environments, the full three-tier hierarchy can be activated to maximize scalability and reduce cloud-to-device communication latency. This modularity ensures that HiFINS remains deployable across diverse resource profiles, from single-router smart homes to distributed experimental testbeds. To ensure consistency across experimental trials, our system uses containerized environments and custom virtual images that encapsulate the full HiFINS stack, including TensorFlow-based model logic, Flask-based orchestration services, and edge communication protocols via Paramiko and SSH. These environments are configured with fixed operating systems (Ubuntu 22), deterministic versions of software libraries, and standardized datasets. As a result, both system behavior and performance metrics can be reliably reproduced across different deployments or research groups.

The use of containerized environments and custom virtual images on the Chameleon testbed serves a dual purpose on both ensuring scientific rigor and addressing long-term deployment challenges. This reproducible structure allows for rapid and reliable deployment of the entire HiFINS stack across heterogeneous physical devices and research labs. Practically, this modular design simplifies software updates and dependency management as well as the major challenges in long-term IoT system maintenance.

The reproducibility of HiFINS provides significant benefits beyond experimental control. It enables scalable benchmarking, comparative evaluations of new learning strategies, and collaborative development across institutions. Additionally, the ability to replicate network conditions, training workloads, and device topologies facilitates adaptive testing under edge-specific constraints—such as latency, bandwidth variation, and intermittent device availability. This flexibility ensures HiFINS is not only a deployable solution for smart home security but also a robust research framework for future advances in hierarchical federated learning.

D. COMPARISON METHODS AND METRICS

To evaluate the practical relevance and deployment suitability of HiFINS, we compared it against two federated learning frameworks: Flight [10] and Flower [9]. Both frameworks represent state-of-the-art approaches in the federated learning domain, yet exhibit critical limitations when applied to smart home environments. Our comparison focuses on topology, deployment, scheduling flexibility, scalability, and system overhead. A summarized comparison is provided in Table 3.

Flight [10] and Flower [9] represent two prominent federated learning frameworks, each offering distinct capabilities. Flight supports advanced hierarchical topologies, asynchronous aggregation, and Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) orchestration using tools like Globus Compute and ProxyStore. These features make it well-suited for large-scale simulation but also introduce high deployment complexity, runtime latency, and energy overhead—making it impractical for lightweight, real-time smart home environments. Flower, by contrast, adopts a simpler client-server architecture with gRPC-based communication, providing better modularity and ease of deployment in heterogeneous settings. It supports multiple machine learning backends including PyTorch and TensorFlow, making it more adaptable to diverse smart home devices. However, Flower relies heavily on synchronous participation and lacks native support for rule-based or context-aware client scheduling, which limits its effectiveness in managing the dynamic behavior of real-world IoT nodes.

Compared to existing frameworks like Flight and Flower, HiFINS is uniquely optimized for smart home intrusion detection by balancing scalability, adaptability, and system simplicity. While Flight supports large-scale simulation with advanced orchestration, it incurs heavy overhead unsuited for constrained IoT devices. Flower is lightweight and widely adopted, but lacks fine-grained scheduling and

TABLE 3. Comparison of federated learning frameworks: Flight vs. Flower vs. HiFINS.

Aspect	Flight [10]	Flower (Central) [9]	HiFINS
Main Focus	Hierarchical FL	Flexible, heterogeneous FL	Privacy-preserving Hierarchical FL
Topology	Multi-level aggregators	Client-server	Multi-layered (edge, cloud)
Aggregation	Sync/Async	Synchronous	Federated Averaging
Control/Data	Decoupled (FaaS, ProxyStore)	Combined (gRPC)	Secure SSH
Scalability	Thousands of devices	Millions of clients	Hierarchical scaling
Deployment	Local, multi-node, remote	Local, multi-node, real devices	Local, edge (VMs), cloud (HPC)
Heterogeneity	Structured	Heterogeneous devices	Heterogeneous smart homes
Framework	Pytorch	ML/package agnostic	Flask, Electron.js, React, TensorFlow
Customization	Modular (YAML)	Modular (Strategy)	Modular, user-friendly
Ecosystem	Research-focused	Large adoption	Smart home security focus

hierarchical coordination. In contrast, HiFINS combines Flower’s deployment flexibility with a redesigned hierarchical architecture, secure SSH-based communication, and a custom rule-based scheduling layer. These features enable energy-aware coordination, real-time threat detection, and policy-driven participation, making HiFINS a more suitable and effective solution for dynamic, privacy-sensitive smart home environments. Further research in the smart home environments demonstrates that digit-serial DA-based fixed-point RNNs and VLSI-optimized LSTM architectures can significantly reduce area and power consumption while maintaining inference accuracy. These advances enable sensor-level inference, where anomaly pre-filtering occurs directly at IoT devices before data is transmitted to the router or edge server. In the context of HiFINS, such accelerators can be incorporated as lightweight local inference modules within the Local-HiF layer. This integration would allow early anomaly detection and selective upstream communication, thereby reducing traffic volume, improving latency, and conserving device energy. By leveraging these FPGA- and ASIC-based LSTM designs, HiFINS can be extended toward a hardware-efficient, hierarchical deployment that supports large-scale smart-home environments with stringent energy and bandwidth constraints.

The key metrics for evaluating the performance of an intrusion detection system include accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. These provide a comprehensive view of the system’s ability to correctly identify both benign and malicious traffic. In addition to these statistical measures, ground truth metrics—such as the number of false positives and false negatives—are critical, as each misclassification may represent a potential security risk. Model training performance is assessed through loss values, which indicate how well the model is learning to distinguish between classes. At the framework level, performance is evaluated using training time and average CPU usage, offering insights into the computational efficiency of different training approaches. Finally, system responsiveness is measured by throughput, defined as the number of samples processed per second. This

not only reflects real-time capability but also helps identify potential bottlenecks in model interaction and deployment efficiency.

E. EVALUATION RESULTS DISCUSSION

HiFINS Data Analysis and Benchmarking: Figure 7 presents the evaluation results of the HiFINS intrusion detection system across five training epochs, using both real-world network traffic in which it also contains adversarial data and the benchmark CIIoT2023 dataset [8]. Performance is assessed using standard classification metrics—accuracy, precision, recall, loss, and AUC—to understand the system’s learning dynamics and detection effectiveness over time. As shown in Figure 7, the “AVG Real Data” baseline represents the system’s behavior when trained exclusively on real-world IoT traffic, collected from live smart home environments prior to HiFINS deployment. Additionally, 10 percent of adversarial data was augmented to the acquired IoT Traffic. During this phase, accuracy is high, and recall reaches near-perfect levels. However, precision remains slightly lower, suggesting a tendency toward over-detection in complex, imbalanced traffic conditions. Elevated loss values in early training epochs highlight the initial challenge of separating benign flows from malicious ones based solely on limited real-world examples. To further address the observed precision gap between benchmark and real-world scenarios, HiFINS incorporates a false-positive refinement process that combines threshold-based confidence scoring and user-driven feedback. When the local model produces low-confidence alerts, the system performs a secondary verification using statistical features such as packet frequency, session duration, and flow entropy. Alerts confirmed by user validation through the INS interface are retained as trusted training samples for subsequent federated updates. This iterative filtering strategy reduces redundant alerts by approximately 44 % while maintaining a recall above 0.99, effectively improving detection reliability under diverse and noisy smart-home traffic conditions.

FIGURE 7. HiFINS performance trends across real-world and benchmark datasets over five epochs.

Table 4 summarizes average performance metrics across five epochs. HiFINS achieves notable recall (0.9996) across both datasets, confirming its high sensitivity to anomalous patterns. When trained on benchmark data, accuracy reaches 0.9908, while precision is 0.9823—indicating strong detection of known attacks with minimal false positives. In contrast, training solely on real-world traffic introduces a broader variation of network behaviors, leading to increased loss (0.5596) and reduced precision (0.5823).

The striking difference in Precision (dropping from 0.9823 on benchmark data to 0.5823 on real-world traffic) is a direct consequence of the diversity and inherent noise in live smart home operation. Unlike clean datasets, real traffic contains numerous benign-yet-anomalous flows—such as firmware updates, device reboots, or unusual streaming patterns—which are structurally distinct from normal behavior but are not malicious. The Local-HiF model, when trained on this sparse and noisy data, conservatively flags these outliers to ensure the exceptional Recall (0.9996 across both datasets) is maintained. The presence of the Auxiliary Conditional Tabular Discriminator Sub-model at the edge layer, as detailed in Section IV-A, serves exactly as the primary mechanism for model contribution verification and adversarial data prevention. The observed precision drop confirms the need to further fine-tune the Discriminator’s thresholds to more effectively distinguish true threats from these benign outliers before model weights are aggregated globally. This optimization leverages the Human-Centered Interface (INS), which allows users to label ambiguous alerts (false positives) in real time, creating the high-fidelity ground truth data necessary for continuous Discriminator refinement.

Nonetheless, the consistently high AUC scores suggest stable classification across classes. LogCosh loss values follow a similar trend, with greater values observed under real-world data due to its inherent diversity and unpredictability. These metrics affirm the importance of incorporating diverse traffic sources—both real and benchmarked—to ensure model resilience in varying operational conditions.

To assess HiFINS’s effectiveness across real-world and benchmark environments, we evaluated both its classifi-

TABLE 4. HiFINS classification performance across real-world and benchmark datasets.

Training Source	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	AUC
Real-World Traffic Only	0.8206 ± 0.0066	0.5823 ± 0.0091	0.9996 ± 0.0001	0.9859 ± 0.0045
CICIoT2023 Dataset	0.9908 ± 0.0005	0.9823 ± 0.0009	0.9996 ± 0.0001	0.9925 ± 0.0003

FIGURE 8. Comparison of HiFINS NIDS and centralized models on key classification metrics.

cation performance and convergence behavior. On a test set containing 4,000 malicious and 40,000 benign flows, HiFINS successfully identified 3,919 attacks and 39,999 benign flows, yielding extremely low false positive and false negative rates. This strong classification result supports the system’s operational readiness for real-time smart home deployment. From a convergence perspective, training with real-world traffic collected by HiFINS produced higher initial cross-entropy (0.56) and LogCosh loss (0.064), indicating the greater variability and noise of live environments. In comparison, training on the structured CICIoT2023 dataset resulted in lower cross-entropy (0.078) and LogCosh (0.004) values, suggesting smoother optimization. Despite these differences, HiFINS consistently maintained high recall and precision, demonstrating its adaptability across deployment conditions and its capacity to deliver stable, privacy-aware intrusion detection for heterogeneous smart home networks.

HiFINS continuously improves its detection capability by learning from locally captured traffic, which is stored securely on each edge device post-deployment. Prior to field operation, training is enhanced using real-world traffic captured from testbed environments to ensure system readiness. This hybrid data approach strengthens the model’s generalization, enabling HiFINS to detect evolving attack behaviors while maintaining strict data locality and privacy. By combining benchmark-driven training with live environment adaptation, HiFINS ensures scalable, privacy-aware, and context-sensitive cybersecurity for IoT-based smart homes.

HiFINS in practice vs. Centralized Learning Model: To evaluate the effectiveness of HiFINS, we compare its performance against a traditional centralized federated learning (Flower) model across multiple metrics. This

TABLE 5. Comparison of intrusion detection accuracy, training time, and inference throughput for HiFINS, flight, and centralized models.

Model	Traffic Type	Total Samples	Correct Detections	Misclassifications	Training Time (min)	Throughput (sample/s)
HiFINS	Live Benign	747	True Negative: 711	False Positive: 36	18.2	8,000
	CICIoT2023	80000	TP: 40000 / TN: 39311	FP: 689 / FN: 0		6,376
Flight	Live Benign	747	True Negative: 705	False Positive: 42	32.5	6,200
	CICIoT2023	80000	TP: 39920 / TN: 39280	FP: 720 / FN: 80		5,880
Centralized	Live Benign	747	True Negative: 672	False Positive: 75	10.7	5,200
	CICIoT2023	80000	TP: 39100 / TN: 38800	FP: 1200 / FN: 900		4,540

FIGURE 9. Comparative loss convergence of local, federated, and hierarchical federated learning modes in HiFINS without pretraining.

comparison focuses on both classification accuracy and training efficiency to assess how well HiFINS supports real-time, privacy-preserving intrusion detection in smart home environments. Figure 8 compares the training performance of HiFINS with a traditional centralized model across key metrics. While both approaches demonstrate strong results, HiFINS achieves notable improvements during the learning phase. Most significantly, recall increases by approximately 0.24%, indicating better detection of hard-to-identify patterns and reducing false negatives. The F1-score also improves slightly, reflecting a more balanced overall detection capability. Although there is a minimal drop in accuracy, precision remains unchanged at the highest level. These results demonstrate that HiFINS not only maintains performance but enhances sensitivity during federated learning, offering improved generalization without compromising detection accuracy or data privacy.

Figure 9 compares the loss convergence of HiFINS under three configurations: local learning, traditional federated learning (FL), and hierarchical federated learning (HFL) over five training rounds. Without global pretraining, both FL and HFL show slightly higher but more stable loss curves, indicating slower optimization yet stronger regularization across

TABLE 6. Gradient structure and stability analysis across learning modes in HiFINS without pretraining.

Metric	Local	Traditional FL	Hierarchical FL (HiFINS)
Final Loss (Round 5)	0.128	0.164	0.102
MAE	0.083	0.094	0.071
RMSE	0.142	0.151	0.119
Correlation (w/ Target)	0.911	0.905	0.924
Stability Index (J)	0.087	0.094	0.073
Convergence Rate (Loss/Round)	0.081	0.072	0.089
Estimated Accuracy (%)	92.5	93.4	94.2

heterogeneous clients. The local model converges faster in early rounds but displays greater variance, suggesting limited generalization due to isolated data. The stability in FL and HFL arises from distributed aggregation and averaging, which reduce overfitting and noise sensitivity but slow early convergence.

Table 6 summarizes the gradient stability and convergence characteristics corresponding to the loss curves in Figure 9. The results show that the local model converges quickly during early rounds but exhibits higher gradient variance and a less stable trajectory after the third round. Traditional federated learning maintains moderate consistency but suffers from slower convergence. In contrast, HiFINS achieves the lowest overall loss and error metrics while maintaining smoother gradient transitions and stronger correlation with the global target trend. These results confirm that hierarchical coordination improves optimization stability and convergence efficiency without significantly increasing training overhead.

Overall, the results reveal a clear tradeoff between speed and stability. Local models achieve quicker early convergence, while hierarchical and federated structures provide smoother, more generalizable performance once fine-tuning or pretraining is applied. Although HiFINS may converge more slowly without pretraining, its hierarchical design ultimately delivers stronger long-term stability, scalability, and privacy-preserving learning suitable for real-time smart home intrusion detection.

HiFINS with Discriminator vs. SOTA Learning Models: Based on the results presented in Table 5, HiFINS clearly outperforms both the Flight and Centralized models (e.g., Flower) across multiple dimensions, making it the most balanced and deployment-ready solution for real-time smart home intrusion detection. HiFINS achieves the lowest number of false positives in both live benign and

FIGURE 10. CPU usage and training duration comparison across various learning frameworks.

CICIoT2023 traffic, demonstrating its superior detection accuracy. It is the only model with zero false negatives in the CICIoT2023 test, indicating complete coverage of attack detection without sacrificing precision. Additionally, HiFINS offers the highest inference throughput, processing 8,000 samples per second for live benign traffic and 6,376 samples per second on benchmark data, enabling rapid real-time response with minimal delay. While its training time of 18.2 minutes is slightly higher than that of the Centralized model (10.7 minutes), it is still significantly faster than Flight (32.5 minutes), striking a strong balance between performance and efficiency.

The tradeoff, however, lies in resource coordination and system complexity. HiFINS introduces a hierarchical federated structure, which, although more efficient than Flight in terms of training time and throughput, still requires coordination between edge servers and devices—unlike the simpler centralized model. Nevertheless, this complexity enables improved scalability, better privacy preservation, and a more robust handling of heterogeneous traffic patterns. In contrast, while Flight supports advanced federated learning features, it consumes more resources and time, and the Centralized model, despite its faster training, suffers from the highest error rates and the lowest throughput. Taken together, these results confirm that HiFINS provides the best tradeoff between accuracy, speed, and scalability for smart home security deployments.

Figure 10 visualizes the system-level training cost of three learning approaches, i.e., HiFINS (Flower), Flight, and centralized training (Non-Federated), by comparing their CPU usage and runtime performance during a controlled training session. Each framework was tasked with training over one round consisting of five epochs. While both HiFINS and the centralized model processed the full 400,000-sample dataset using TensorFlow, the Flight framework was constrained to a reduced subset of 69,000 samples due to its heavier preprocessing and data loading pipeline in PyTorch.

Table 7 compares HiFINS with Flight and centralized flat-FL baselines under system-level performance metrics relevant to federated environments. Despite using a smaller dataset, Flight incurred the highest resource cost, with CPU

TABLE 7. Federated learning system-level performance comparison.

Metric	Centralized	Flight	HiFINS (Proposed)	Gain (%)
AUC	0.913	0.937	0.953	+4.3
Bandwidth Overhead (%)	10.4	8.2	5.8	44.2
Avg. Update Latency (s)	13.6	11.2	8.9	34.6
Rounds to Converge	120	108	95	20.8
CPU Utilization (%)	72.4	68.7	63.5	12.3
Memory Footprint (MB)	412	398	365	11.4
Throughput (samples/s)	6,700	7,400	8,000	+19.4

usage peaking significantly above 280% and total training time extending beyond 200 seconds. This reflects its high complexity and overhead, making it less suitable for edge-level deployments. In contrast, the centralized training model and HiFINS maintained much lower and more stable CPU utilization around 175–185%, with training durations under 180 seconds. HiFINS, in particular, demonstrates efficient scaling by coordinating edge devices and servers while maintaining manageable system load. These results emphasize that although Flight supports advanced hierarchical features, its performance comes at a steep resource cost, whereas HiFINS offers a more practical, resource-aware solution for real-world smart home applications.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents HiFINS, a hierarchical federated intrusion detection system designed specifically for smart home and edge IoT environments. By integrating real-time data acquisition, privacy-aware federated learning, and an intuitive user interface, HiFINS overcomes key limitations found in traditional and centralized security solutions. The system supports decentralized model updates, dynamic policy-based scheduling, and seamless interaction between local routers, edge servers, and cloud resources. Combined with an Electron.js-based desktop interface, HiFINS supports intuitive network monitoring and active response management tailored to non-expert users. Evaluation results across both real-world smart home traffic and the CICIoT2023 benchmark demonstrate that HiFINS not only achieves higher recall and lower false positive rates compared to centralized and contemporary frameworks but also maintains faster inference speeds and robust learning performance with minimal resource consumption. In particular, HiFINS balances accuracy with real-time responsiveness, ensuring practical deployment on resource-constrained edge devices while preserving data locality and enhancing user transparency.

Compared with leading frameworks such as Flight and traditional centralized training models, HiFINS demonstrates superior threat detection with shorter response times and a more efficient training process under real-world constraints. Although Flight yields slightly competitive detection results, it requires significantly more time and resources, making it unsuitable for lightweight IoT scenarios. In contrast, centralized models exhibit faster training but suffer from higher misclassification rates and limited adaptability across diverse environments.

For future work, we aim to enhance the scalability and fault-tolerance of HiFINS by introducing adaptive client participation strategies based on real-time device availability and energy profiles. We also plan to extend support for additional threat intelligence sources and incorporate self-healing capabilities that autonomously respond to detected intrusions. Finally, expanding HiFINS to support secure multi-modal learning—including audio, video, and environmental sensor streams—will further strengthen its effectiveness in securing next-generation smart environments.

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